

Advertising Composition Selection Strategy to Strengthen the Language Message in Skincare Advertising on Tiktok

Asya Zahra^{1*}, Reni Amali², Aisya Fatihah T.A³, Muh Ary Fauzi⁴, Muh Takwin⁵
Agricultural Technology Education, Makassar State University
Corresponding Author: Asya Zahra zahraasya046@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to explain the composition of advertisements presented in advertising promotions on TikTok. The data source in this research is a TikTok video containing skincare advertisements for several products, namely skintific and lacoco dark spot. There are 3 points of advertising composition that must be considered, namely the main point consisting of an attractive ad title, stunning visuals, tagline, the body of the ad consisting of a product description and before and after and the closing of the ad consisting of a Call to Action (CTA), Logo and Information Contacts, testimonials and price mentions. However, it can be seen that the most dominant message content in skincare is stunning visuals, product descriptions and testimonials, because this is the key that can attract the audience to use it. So overall, the strategy for selecting ad composition on TikTok must consider visual strength, product delivery and testimonials. With a careful approach, skincare advertising can successfully strengthen language messages and achieve the desired marketing objectives.

INTRODUCTION

In the ever-evolving digital era, social media platforms have played a key role in brands' efforts to market their products and services. TikTok, as a very popular short video-based platform, has become an attractive place for skincare brands to promote their products. One very important element in advertising is the ability to convey a strong language message to the audience. Effective language messages in skincare advertising are becoming increasingly important because they can influence consumer purchasing decisions and create a long-lasting brand impression. Therefore, this research aims to explore and analyze advertising composition selection strategies that can strengthen the language message in skincare advertisements on TikTok.

The skincare industry has experienced rapid growth over the past few years. Awareness of the importance of skin care and personal appearance has increased, triggering an increase in demand for skincare products. Skincare brands compete fiercely to reach a wider audience and get consumer attention. In the context of TikTok, a platform that is very popular among the younger generation, skincare brands are competing to take advantage of the marketing potential of this platform. However, facing increasing numbers of competitors and keeping up with fast-changing trends on TikTok is a challenge in itself.

Choosing ad composition is a key element in the marketing strategy for skincare brands on TikTok. TikTok is a short video-based platform, so brands have to condense their message into a very limited time while maintaining the appeal and effectiveness of the ad. Therefore, this research will identify the most effective advertising composition selection strategy in strengthening the language message in skincare advertisements on TikTok. This research will provide valuable insight for skincare marketers seeking to create more effective and persuasive advertising on the platform.

In addition, TikTok is a unique platform with features that allow content creators to innovate in creating unique advertisements. There are various elements in ad composition, including music selection, visual layout, ad length, narrative style, and more, that can influence how language messages are conveyed and received by viewers. Therefore, this research will explore these various elements to determine the best combination that will strengthen the language message in the context of skincare advertising on TikTok.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

The skincare industry has experienced rapid growth over the past few years. Awareness of the importance of skin care and personal appearance has increased, triggering an increase in demand for skincare products. Skincare brands compete fiercely to reach a wider audience and get consumer attention. In the context of TikTok, a platform that is very popular among the younger generation, skincare brands are competing to take advantage of the marketing potential of this platform. However, facing increasing numbers of competitors and keeping up with fast-changing trends on TikTok is a challenge in itself.

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appeal and effectiveness of the ad. Therefore, this research will identify the most effective advertising composition selection strategy in strengthening the language message in skincare advertisements on TikTok. This research will provide valuable insight for skincare marketers seeking to create more effective and persuasive advertising on the platform.

METHODOLOGY

To achieve the objectives of this research, the research method used will include content analysis of skincare advertisements on TikTok. We will collect samples of skincare ads from various brands active on TikTok. After that, we will analyze each ad to identify the compositional elements used, such as music selection, visual layout, ad duration, narrative style, and more. The data source in this research is a TikTok video containing skincare advertisements for several products, namely skintific and lacoco dark spot. This product was chosen as a research source because it is considered to be very trending on the TikTok application, and can provoke consumer responses or feedback through comments or reviews on TikTok. This aims to obtain absolute data, as well as make it easier to record the analysis of the advertising composition used in the skincare advertising video.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Advertising is persuasive communication delivered through various media with the aim of promoting a particular product, service, brand or message to a target audience. Advertising aims to influence consumer attitudes, behavior, or decisions, whether to buy a product or service, support an issue, or simply increase awareness about a brand or message. Advertisements can contain visual, text, audio, and/or interactive elements designed to attract attention, convey a message, and create a positive impression of what is being promoted.

Advertisements have a crucial role in strengthening language messages and attracting consumer interest, especially when implemented on platforms like TikTok which are very dynamic and focus on short videos. Here is how advertising plays a role in achieving this goal:

1. **Visual Creativity:** In TikTok ads, visual creativity plays an important role in reinforcing the language message. Compelling visual elements, such as creative layouts, impressive visual effects, and clever use of color, can capture the viewer's attention, which in turn strengthens the message being conveyed. For example, using creative transition effects or animations can make language messages more interesting and memorable.
2. **Music and Sound:** The right choice of background music or background sound can provide an emotional nuance that supports the language message. Songs or sounds that match the brand or product can create positive associations in the viewer's mind, which helps in reinforcing the message and creating appeal.
3. **Compelling Short Stories:** TikTok is known for its creative short story format. Ads on these platforms often utilize a compelling narrative, which

may include a “quick story” that keeps viewers engaged and wanting to see the ad through to the end. This helps in associating the language message with a memorable experience.

4. Fit with TikTok Trends: TikTok is always flooded with trending trends and challenges. Ads that can adapt to the latest trends on TikTok are more likely to get viewers' attention. This involves selecting compositional elements that suit current trends.
5. Interaction and Participation: TikTok allows ads to be more interactive. Ads can encourage viewers to participate in challenges or take part in trendy voting cuts. This not only reinforces the language message, but also increases audience engagement and engagement.
6. Selection of Relevant Language: Selection of simple and easy to remember keywords is important in TikTok advertising. Language that is relevant to the target audience should be used to ensure the message is well received.

Ads on TikTok have great potential to combine creative elements with strong language messages and capture consumer interest. With a deep understanding of TikTok's audience and platform trends, advertising can be an effective tool in achieving this goal.

The results of this research are regarding the composition or elements used in the strategy to strengthen language messages in skincare advertisements on the TikTok application. Based on research that has been carried out regarding advertising composition selection strategies to strengthen language messages in skincare advertisements on TikTok, there are 2 data on skincare advertisements on TikTok that use ad composition selection strategies to strengthen language messages so that the audience is interested in using the product.

The following is the ad composition data for skincare ads on TikTok, divided into 3 items, namely the main item, the ad body and the conclusion as the ad structure.

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1. Skintific

In the product advertisement "Skintific," the composition of the advertisement can be divided into three main parts: the main point, the body of the advertisement, and the conclusion of the advertisement. The following is a discussion of each part:

a. Main Items

The main point of an advertisement is the element that is first introduced to the viewer and aims to attract attention. In the context of Skintific products, the main points can focus on the following elements:

- 1) Attractive Ad Title: The main point begins with an attractive and short ad title that can describe the benefits of Skintific products.
- 2) Stunning Visuals: The first visual in the ad can display the Skintific product in an attractive way, such as the product bottle or an image of healthy skin.

3) *Taglines*: Can include a tagline that emphasizes the benefits of the product or brand, with the Skintific product tagline, namely "We Repair Your Skin Barrier" which means that Skintific products are intended to repair damaged skin barriers and strengthen them.

b. Advertising Agency

The advertising body is the main part used to convey the product message in more detail. In the context of Skintific products, the advertising body may include the following elements:

- 1) *Product Description*: Describes the product "Skintific," including key ingredients, benefits, and how to use. This may include an explanation of how the product helps improve skin health. Skintific products have main ingredients that are classified as active, namely ceramide, hyaluronic acid, and centella asiatica, these ingredients are found in Skintific moisturizer products. Where the benefit is to overcome damaged skin barrier problems such as acne, redness, textured skin, and also dry skin quickly but still safe for the skin barrier. Meanwhile, how to use it is to use it morning and evening after cleansing your face. This product is claimed to be safe for all skin types.
- 2) *Before and after*: in the Skintific product advertisement using before and after, the content creator shows the appearance of his face before and after using the Skintific product, this is a strategy used to attract consumer confidence that by using the product his face will be healthy like the content creator in the advertisement.
- 3) *User Testimonials*: Skintific products, especially moisturizer products, display testimonials or reviews from users who are satisfied with the product to strengthen consumer trust.

c. Ad Cover:

The conclusion of an ad is the part that directs viewers to a specific action. In the context of Skintific products, an advertising cover may include the following elements:

- 1) *Call to Action(CTA)*: Invites viewers to take action, such as purchasing a product, signing up for a special offer, or visiting the Skintific website.
- 2) *Logo and Contact Information*: Displays the "Skintific" logo and contact information such as phone number or website address for easy access.
- 3) *Mention of Prices or Special Offers*: in skintific product advertisements it is very clear to state the price of each product, such as the moisturizer product, the content creator states the price, namely Rp. 136,000 with the blue color variant which is suitable for oily and acne-prone skin, while the pink variant is priced at Rp. 136,000, this variant is suitable for Kusama and acne-prone skin.

By dividing "Skintific" ads into these three parts, companies can ensure that the product message is conveyed effectively, captures attention, provides relevant information and calls viewers to action. This helps in achieving the advertising objectives of the product "Skintific" in a persuasive and informative manner.

2. *Lacoco Dark Spot*

In the "Lacoco Dark Spot" product advertisement, the composition of the advertisement can be divided into three main parts: the main point, the body of the advertisement, and the closing of the advertisement. The following is a discussion of each section:

a. Main Items

The main point of an advertisement is the element that is first introduced to the viewer and aims to attract attention. In the context of Lacoco dark spot products, the main points can focus on the following elements:

- 1) **Attractive Ad Title:** The main point begins with an attractive and short ad title that can describe the benefits of the Lacoco dark spot product. Where the title of the advertisement emphasizes that Lacoco Dark Spot is an exfoliating essence and serum that can remove dead skin, clean pores and brighten the face.
- 2) **Stunning Visuals:** The first visual in the advertisement shows the Lacoco Dark Spot product which uses a tiny purple and black bottle with a size of 12ml. At the beginning of the video, the content creator also briefly explains the benefits and how to use it.
- 3) **Taglines:** Can include a tagline that emphasizes the benefits of the product or brand, with the Lacoco Dark Spot product tagline being "En Nature" which means providing products produced from . This Lacoco product is a beauty product that was founded in 2017. The Lacoco brand itself comes from the word coconut or coconut which has the philosophy of "a tree for all benefits". Every Lacoco product, one of which is Lacoco Dark Spot, is formulated with high quality natural ingredients, and is made for everyone to get young, healthy and radiant looking skin.
- 4) **User Testimonials:** Lacoco Darkspot products display testimonials at the beginning of the video. Not in the advertising body. In the testimonials, there were those who stated that "Lacoco Darkspot really works, bro", "it's really true, I've tried it, but I use it sparingly, only 3 times a week, but I swear it has a really great effect on my face," "it's really effective. lacoco", and "I've also become really good at it huhu". By displaying testimonials, the audience will become more curious and interested in using them. Because in general the audience on the Tiktok application relies on testimonials as proof that the product is worthy, and useful for their current facial needs, and can cure their facial problems.

b. Advertising Agency

The advertising body is the main part used to convey the product message in more detail. In the context of Lacoco Darkspot products, the advertising body may include the following elements:

- 1) **Product Description:** Explains the Lacoco Darkspot product's main ingredients, benefits and how to use it. Where the main content of Lacoco darkspot is exfoliator consisting of AHA, BHA, PHA to remove dead skin cells, and clean the face down to the pores. The content creator also explains how to use it, namely to use it at night after cleansing your face, when applying it to your face, only use 4 drops and 2 times a week and it is

recommended to use sunscreen in the morning before doing activities because this Lacoco product is an ESFO product, so to minimize irritation it is recommended use sunscreen in the morning

- 2) *Before and after*: in the Lacoco dark spot product advertisement using before and after, the content creator shows the appearance of his face before and after using the Lacoco product. The before appearance shows a face that looks dull, has large pores, and there are several blackish acne scars, whereas after 2 weeks of use, changes can be seen on the face, namely the pores are disguised, the acne scars fade and the skin looks bright. This is a strategy used to attract consumer confidence that by using the product their face will be as healthy as the content creator in the advertisement.

c. Ad Cover:

The conclusion of an ad is the part that directs viewers to a specific action. In the context of Lacoco dark spot products, advertising cover may include the following elements:

- 1) *Call to Action*(CTA): At the end of the video, the content creator invites the audience to try Lacoco Dark Spot for skin problems as stated previously in the body of the advertisement. This dark spot is a local product worth it
- 4) Logo and Contact Information: Lacoco Dark Spot does not display logo and contact information at the end of the video.

Mention of Price or Special Offer: at the end of the video the content creator says that the price of Lacoco is IDR 189,000, but Lacoco often holds price reduction promotions so that the price of this Lacoco dark spot is IDR. 150,000.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the research results, it can be concluded that advertising composition has an important role in promoting skincare products and strengthening the language message. There are 3 points of advertising composition that must be considered, namely the main point consisting of an attractive ad title, stunning visuals, tagline, the body of the ad consisting of a product description and before and after and the closing of the ad consisting of a Call to Action (CTA), Logo and Information Contacts, testimonials and price mentions. However, it can be seen that the most dominant message content in skincare is stunning visuals, product descriptions and testimonials, because this is the key that can attract the audience to use it. So overall, the strategy for selecting ad composition on TikTok must consider visual strength, product delivery and testimonials. With a careful approach, skincare advertising can successfully strengthen language messages and achieve the desired marketing goals.

FURTHER STUDY

Every research is subject to limitations; thus, you can explain them here and briefly suggest further investigations.

REFERENCES

- Azizah Des Derivanti, MI, Wahidin, DW, & Warouw, DM (2022). Phenomenological Study: Consumer Behavior in Purchasing Decisions for Skincare Products Through Digital Platform Media in the Covid-19 Era. *Sibatik Journal: Scientific Journal in the Social, Economic, Cultural, Technological and Educational Sectors*, 1(9), 1617-1628.
- Haryadi, T., Rahmasari, EA, & Yogananti, AF (2023). Education on Design Composition and Advertising Content for Lumintu Umkm. *Abdimasku: Journal of Community Service*, 6(2), 317-322.
- Inderasari, E., Hapsari, DA, Rosita, FY, & Ulya, C. (2021). Analysis of the Use of Language Style in Social Media-wise Public Service Advertisements on Surakarta City Radio. *Kembara: Scientific Journal of Language, Literature and Teaching*, 7(2), 508-528.
- Liantika, Dhania Aryu, Dewi Kusumaningsih, and Wahyu Dini Septiari. "Strategy for Selecting Ad Composition to Strengthen the Language Message in Skincare Ads on Tiktok." *Aksara: Scientific Journal of Indonesian Language and Literature Education* 7.1 (2023): 50-56.
- Priatama, R., Ramadhan, IH, Akalili, A., & Kulau, F. (2021). Analysis of Digital Marketing Techniques on the Tiktok Application (Case Study of the Tiktok@ Jogjafoodhunterofficial Account). *Socia: Journal of the Social Sciences*, 18(1), 49-60.
- Susanti, Y., Tyas, DK, & Saputra, BA (2021). Language Style and Persuasive Techniques in Toothpaste Advertisements on YouTube in 2020. *Kansasi Journal: Journal of Indonesian Language Education and Indonesian Literature*, 6(2), 90-101.
- Syauki, WR, & Avina, DAA (2020). Perceptions and Preferences for Skincare Use among Millennial Women from a Marketing Communications Perspective. *Journal of Communication Management*, 4(2), 42-60.
- Zakharova, G. (2020). Search For Persuasive Strategies In Tourism Advertising Discourse. *Journal Of Vasyl Stefanyk Precarpathian National University*, 7(3), 7-18.